

Résumé for Researchers (R4R) (Narrative CV): Alternative Uses Group (AUG) Terms of Reference

Aims and objectives

- To explore, test and evaluate the alternative application of the narrative CV based on the four boxes detailing contributions from the Résumé for Researchers (R4R) template.
- To identify alternative applications of the narrative CV, outside of grant funding decisions. For example, in recruitment and promotion.
- To contribute to the sharing of best practice in alternative uses of the narrative CV as a tool to shift what is visible and valued and accelerate culture change in a cohesive way.
- To address challenges in applying the R4R in all settings to allow practical action to be taken.
- Where possible, to agree aligned approaches to the resources, evidence and training which support its wider adoption and use in alternative applications.
- To establish a shared evaluation framework to support ongoing adoption and evolution internationally and cross- sector.
- To contribute to a resource and evidence base.
- To inform support materials.
- To share lessons learnt and best practice.
- To contribute to an international conference on R4R (narrative CV).
- To avoid duplication with other groups.
- To build communication and relationships between organisations.
- To learn about what each organisation is doing on emerging issues.

Meeting principles

- Discussion will follow Chatham House rules (explicit/agree where not).
- Minutes will capture general discussion only and not individual/organisational contributions except where agreed. Minutes will be circulated via email to attendees for review. The group will raise an objection or approve the previous meeting's minutes at the next meeting.
- Members will advise associated organisations/teams of meeting discussions. This may involve approaching specific business areas, such as the organisation's recruitment team, to inform and discuss next steps.
- The group will not make decisions on behalf of other members. Group suggestions will be handled within each organisation on an individual basis.
- Some topics may be better discussed within a subset of the group and harness diverse expertise from others within the participating organisations. These time- limited sub-groups would feed back to the main body.
- The group should avoid overlap with existing cross-organisation groups but will tap into them when we raise shared issues.

Group Management

- The secretariat will be held by [Universities UK \(UUK\)](#) and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) with chairmanship provided by UUK.
- The group will meet every two months.
- All meetings will be virtual until at least April 2022, or in person at the agreement of the group.
- Substitute reps may attend from each organisation at any meeting but will not be added to the general contact list. Two attendees from an organisation are usually preferable to allow a wide range of organisations to engage. However, more than two attendees from an organisation are acceptable if a specific agenda item requires it.

Membership

Full Name	Job Title	Organisation
Daniel Wake (Chair)	Policy Manager	Universities UK
Dana Gamble	Policy Researcher	Universities UK
Hilary Noone	Research & Innovation Culture Lead	UKRI
Ruhena Begum	Senior Strategy Advisor	UKRI